

ISic0875

I.Sicily inscription 0875

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---ἀνδριδέσῃςμορφῆς]
2. [τρισοῦςλί]πες ἔκτυπα ΙΑΙ[---]
3. [πί]στιν διένειμα □ [---]
4. [ἐ]π' ἐμῆ παράκοι[τι---]
5. [β]ιότοιο ετ[] [---]

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492503

EDCS 39102030

PHI 140354

PHI 316303

Bibliography

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- Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 238
- Libertini, G 1930. Il Museo Biscari. Milan. At 317 no.2

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